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AI R&D for Real Factory

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Abstract

With increase of computational performance of computers AI becomes a really powerful toolbox. The question which tool for which application is decided by trial and error and experience with successful applications. Examples shown stem from different application fields in manufacturing as chatter avoidance, process parameter optimization, compensation, fault detection. Applications also demonstrate the challenge of data acquisition and the limits of scarce data. A possibility to overcome the limits is physics informed AI. Also federated learning and its future role for fractal manufacturing discussed. A visionary overview on future machine tool performance is also provided as guideline. where the complexity of manufacturing processes is handled within the manufacturing machine and a simplistic front end is presented to the operator, which means that major elements of operators' tasks are fulfilled by the intelligence of the machine. In this context not only the task distribution between operators and machine tools needs to be re-iterated, but also the communication with the machine will change.

1. Introduction vision of intelligent machine tool

Manufacturing processes and manufacturing systems composed from process, workpiece, machine and automation are complex. A “keep it simple” approach is only valuable as long the complexity of the process is still taken into account and avoids only overengineering. And this means that the only possibility dealing with complex processes is to re-distribute the complexity between machine and operator. Towards the operator especially unskilled operators the machine shall hide the complexity and make things appear simple. But that means that the machine itself must comply with the full complexity also under weird situations and is paralleled with the efforts towards driver assistance systems and autonomous driving in the automotive industry. Decades of research have struggled with the topic of productivity increase and searching for optimized process parameters, leaving the field in the end to experienced and well skilled operators. The timely development of Artificial Intelligence (AI), computational performance and exchange of big data makes the autonomously operating manufacturing machine appear realistic though being still a vision.

A concept for such an intelligent manufacturing machine is developed and shown in Figure 1, which is capable of learning from different sources. Though the figure shows a milling machine, the same concept can be setup for any other manufacturing process. This system is bio-intelligent as defined by [4] because it contains a central intelligence which is connected to a large number of sensors providing an image of the system and its environment, which is intended to be as complete as possible, so that together with physical models a digital twin of the machine, process and part is established. A large number of sensors are interconnected with the central intelligence and with each other enabling sensor fusion and partial redundancy for fail safe behavior. Different task adapted artificial intelligence tools like different variants

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of neural networks (ANN, CNN, VNN) or more specialized neural network structures as the long short term memory network (LSTM), Markov and rule based decision processes, decision trees (DT), fuzzy inference systems (FIS, ANFIS), k-nearest neighbor (kNN), genetic algorithm (GA) classifiers, support vector machines (SVM), etc. are installed for different tasks of the system to keep autonomy up. But also, physical models need to be exploited to provide already explored knowledge on interdependencies. The system further needs to adapt to different situations. An overview on self-adaptive systems and a collection of technologies for the sake of autonomy is provided in [24]. The mainstream of information exploited by the machine is coming from own observations, which means that a powerful monitoring system for the process must be available. The important properties of the workpiece, which means dimensions, shape, surface roughness and changes of the substructure need to be detected from the equipment. Furthermore, signals of any kind out of the process zone might help to understand the status of the process and machine and give indirect information on the outcoming results. Utilisation of this information can be done in terms of a closed loop control, meaning that it is immediately fed back into the process parameter values as cutting speed and feedrate and coolant supply. A second closed loop cycle takes up the measurements of the generated geometry and surface and is then capable to provide some corrections to the same or the next geometry to be manufactured. The third cycle is the machine learning cycle, which stores the relevant process parameters together with the achieved properties for training of any intended data base for instance a neural network being part of the expert system of the machine. The information can then later on be retrieved for the setup of a different, but somehow related manufacturing task. This threefold approach also represents the time frames, namely immediate impact in the process, correction directly after the process and learning for future tasks. The required expert system differs from standard expert systems, which are used since some 50 years such that it is equipped with learning and reasoning abilities and ideally based on ontology structures. The algorithms behind can be as simple as interpolation and regression methods but always require an indicator for the user to declare whether the data just a guess or proven in some validation procedure.

Figure 1: Concept of an intelligent manufacturing machine integrating operator's capabilities for increased autonomy

Highest priority has the communication with the operator. Companies are relying on a wealth of implicit knowledge of their employees, which can only be safeguarded with the help of an expert system that is able to learn from the inputs, setup of processes from experienced operators. As setup of the process the manufacturing strategy and the individual process parameters are understood. The whole required information with the individual case must be handed over into the machine to make the process run. Missing is that the machine resp. the expert system must generate autonomously an understanding to apply the available knowledge to similar cases. This is the task of the "learning machine". On the other hand, the

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machine needs to be able to use the acquired knowledge to propose setups for new manufacturing tasks for an unskilled user. A crucial point is to distinguish between the inputs of skilled and unskilled operators, which needs to be done with plausibility checks out of the acquired process understanding. All experience based human knowledge has a certain degree of uncertainty, which must be mirrored in the expert system. The uncertainty of knowledge must be attributed to each piece of information within the expert system. This critical topic of teaming between machines and operators is discussed in chapter 2. Fleet- and transfer learning requires besides internet connectivity technologies to transfer results found on one machine to the other. This is even on the level of machines of the same type not yet satisfactorily solved and discussed in chapter 9.

Monitoring of the machine's status is one of the requirements for increased autonomy and predictive maintenance, which today is discussed for all the manufacturing equipment. But also process monitoring and monitoring of the manufacturing quality sheds light on the machine status. In chapter 6 the temperature impact on the accuracy of parts is discussed and in chapter 8 detection of grinding burn as quality issue is one indication that maintenance of the grinding wheel must take place.

The description shows stringently that the technology planning needs to be part of the intelligence of the machine, and either the CAM tool has a bi-directional interface to the machine tool be fed and exploited by it, or the CAM tool is tailored directly to the machine. The future belongs to fully integrated intelligent manufacturing systems. Fully integrating different information channels, sensors and actuators with AI tools, knowledge base (experience) and reasoning capabilities are required to achieve similar properties like highly developed biological (living) systems and exploit their benefits. A more elaborate bio-intelligent powder bed based additive manufacturing system is described in [41]. Being still a vision in its full elaboration already realized achievements in the direction of this goal and their already visible benefits for manufacturing are rolled out in the remainder of the paper.

2. Communication between operators and machines

The third and most powerful source of information are the operators, the most difficult to retrieve though. An example of how to capture tacit knowledge of skilled operators for robot belt grinding is demonstrated for the interactive generation of a toolpath and tool orientations for robot belt grinding [26]. This also shows that humans have from experience some detrimental properties:

1. In order to share their knowledge, humans need a sufficient incentive, preferably a direct benefit for the task they are currently fulfilling.
2. Grinding operators take decisions in a context, that is obvious for them, but needs to be fully described, e.g. complemented with metadata, in order to contribute to a knowledge database.
3. Lower skilled operators, i.e. apprentices, are more likely to benefit from expert systems, but are unlikely to contribute to a learning process, i.e. beneficiaries are unlikely to be the contributors.
4. Information needs validation in order to avoid false, misleading advice that casts doubt on a digital assistant.

Point 1 is generally approached by providing a working environment with different tools, only a part of which is targeted at direct knowledge acquisition, many of them providing helpful services to the operator and eventually harvesting knowledge as a by-product. Point 2 does not add another quality, but raises the threshold for cooperation, since the operator is obliged to provide supplementary information, unknown by the system but vital for the learning process. Due to the large parameter space in grinding processes, a realistic approach is to divide and restrict to grinding specific features, facilitating the operator's necessary input by templates, and making assumptions for missing information.

Point 3 needs a closer look at the shopfloor context, that may include several operators working on the same or similar machine tool, sharing information with peers, and being part of a workflow. Humans have different levels of skills, which clearly indicates the necessity for machine learning approaches, because as can be seen the expert system of the machine was inferior to the best human operator. Figure 2 visualizes the IFIP (International Federation for Information Processing) interaction model that conceptualizes the context of the human-machine interaction, introduced by [14] already in 1991. Although generic, it makes obvious that machine tools equipped with intelligent agents interact with the outer shells of the model, dealing with workflow and interaction between humans as well.

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Figure 2: Left: Framework for Humane-machine interaction known as IFIP model, introduced by [14]. Right: Conceptualization of experimental learning [15].

This understanding can partially pave the way for solutions in response to the above point 3. Experienced and loyal operators have a high interest in perpetuating their knowledge in the company to contribute to the overall success, and therefore passing knowledge from the outermost shell into working procedures and finally into the machine's knowledge database. Finally point 4 is a common problem of all business models based on the accumulation of user information: It must be reviewed, checked for plausibility, today generally by humans, assisted by data analytics for anomaly detection and clustering. Variants of the approach assign confidence levels to parameter sets, depending on their plausibility, completeness of inputs, frequency of occurrence of similar ones, qualification of the source, validation by authorised instances, etc. which is a task suited well for humans and less for the machine. The expectation though is that less skilled operators tend to use the machine in teaching mode, which makes it easier for the operator. Nevertheless, approaches are also discussed to give the decision who is allowed to teach the machine to the company, requiring a personal identification at the machine.

The difficulty of the learning process is not only caused by the above four points, but first of all by the learning itself. Figure 2 right shows a conceptualization of learning from experience according to [15]: "Experimental learning is a process of constructing knowledge that involves a creative tension among the four learning modes. This process is portrayed as an idealized learning cycle or spiral where the learner "touches all the bases"—experiencing, reflecting, thinking, and acting—in a recursive process that is responsive to the learning situation and what is being learned." In case of the learning machine as suggested in Figure 1 "the learner", i. e. the machine, must basically be able to take over the learning cycle, using prescribed use cases and procedures, templates and selective human support.

Machine intelligence must also be seen in terms of the autonomy of a manufacturing process. In contrast to parameter finding, which is probably the most demanding task in this context and only difficult to accomplish, when it comes to increasing autonomy, an intelligent machine can offer the user considerable advantages. Signal analysis, anomaly detection and clustering of faulty conditions are tasks that can be performed, or at least supported and documented, by machines even with incomplete contextual information. The collaboration of the machine with the human operator shall be as easy as possible which means that the machine must be able to utilise the information which the operator is giving anyway to specify and setup the process. This then is in the best case a fully specified point in the multidimensional space of process parameters. In other cases, the information is incomplete and then the expert system of the machine must provide the missing information as the most probable value. From process monitoring the validation of the process setup is gained. As indicated in Figure 1 the operators can be in this concept distinguished as masters or apprentices according to the estimated usefulness of the data provided for some process. It is then also necessary to have for each data specifying the process an indication of the truth level. This then needs for each developed setup be provided to the operator to indicate the probability of a successful process. It is necessary that the monitoring system is then capable to judge the success of the process and by that validate the process parameters. Incomplete and doubtful data sets are kept in the vault of process specifications indicated as doubtful until they become validated.

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3. The role of monitoring and sensors

Without any doubt, data-based modelling, AI, machine learning (ML) relies on the quality of data. Any ML project starts with a discussion of sensors and the quality of delivered data. It is therefore necessary to explore the accessible process data for each process. Full field sensors, which are capable to collect multiple data streams are especially for AI applications of importance, as the information content in the signal streams can be distilled out without necessary prior physical knowledge of the signal generation. Optical signals exploited in image recognition technologies contain information of frequency, intensity, time and space. The same holds true for acoustics, which makes both of them a 6-dimensional space gathered with limited expenditure. Image recognition provides a large amount of pre-trained analysis tools mainly on the basis of convolutional NN which can be adapted to the task at hand by limited training expenditure which is the most prominent application of transfer learning. Acoustic signals can be pre-filtered by mechanical means, before they are captured by the sensor and then translated in electric signals. This means that the transfer function of the signal path from the point of emission to the sensor can be used to increase the information to noise ratio before running with the full sound into the saturation limit of the sensor. Air borne sound and structure born sound (AE) can thus contain different information content. This is exploited for instance in chapter 8. For different processes sensor maps for selection of signals and sensors have been developed as for instance shown in [18] for grinding and in [41] for powder bed additive manufacturing, while sensor capabilities for this are also compared in [11] and [21]. In most cases the possibilities of application, the detectability of exceptions and subsequential strategies of interaction are insufficiently researched. Figure 3 illustrates the process chain from the sensor to the value generation of a data-driven model.

Figure 3: From sensor signals to data-based value delivery in manufacturing nach [8].

As a sensor example developed within the EU-MARS project building on AI image recognition, the setup illustrated below shows optical tool wear detection on a mill-turn center. An optical microscope was placed inside the machine, protected by a housing. To remove cooling lubricants and wear particles from the cutting tool, a compressed air nozzle was used. After cleaning the cutting tool, an image was taken by the microscope on the machine.

A pre-trained U-Net deep learning model was then used for segmentation. The result of the segmentation is the green shaded area, which is classified as tool wear. Based on edge detection and the segmented area, a VB value for the wear can be calculated. This on-machine measurement setup allows for intermittent wear assessment, enabling cost-efficient tool replacement. The tool can be used longer compared to static tool life intervals, which require a high safety margin to account for uncertainties.

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Figure 4: Automatic wear detection based on image segmentation

4. Physics informed AI

One way to mitigate the data requirement for training the AI models is to integrate physical and process related prior-knowledge into the model [22].

There exist various options and approaches to integrate the prior knowledge. Figure 5 shows five different possibilities to include physical relations into NNs. A Physics informed AI utilizes analytical or numerical physics-based models within the AI framework. For example, [31] proposed the Physics Informed model training (PIMT), where the partial differential equations are directly integrated into the cost function. Besides the reduction of the amount of required training data, the generalizability and reliability of the predictions is expected to increase, because the predictions must satisfy the underlying physical equations. On the other side, the computational cost increases during the training since the cost function must be evaluated at each iteration [13].

Figure 5: Classification of physics supported NN [10].

While physics-supported model training or physics-informed model input (PIMI) uses simulation technology to generate the data for training, physical laws can be used to derive further input variables from process parameters. For physics-supported training, results that violate applicable physical laws are penalized. Further approaches account for the solution of the physical differential equations by implementing activation functions that directly represent the solution of the physical problem [1] (PIMC). Physics informed approaches are increasingly adopted also in more complex model structures such as Generative Adversarial Networks [42]. Within Physics-informed model architectures (PIMA) the transformations and their parameters are designed to be trainable and are adjusted during the training

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process to minimize the loss function. To facilitate this optimization using gradient descent algorithms, the transformations must be smoothly differentiable. For example [17] introduced a model that replaces the traditional first layer with a continuous wavelet convolutional layer. Finally, the output of the model and the related Physics-informed model outputs (PIMO) emphasize the interpretability of model predictions rather than incorporating prior knowledge into the model itself. This focus aligns with the growing trend towards explainable AI (XAI), which has become increasingly important in recent years and is a promising approach for manufacturing applications [23]. The combination of real production data with physics-informed architectures enables the effective development of models that capture the actual process, while accounting for physical relations. These approaches enhance the explainability of the models and ultimately increases trust in their predictions.

5. The Bayesian Approach for parameter optimization

Parameter optimization is in production a really time consuming task which often leaves the manufacturing process in an unoptimized state. Utilisation of Gaussian process models and Bayesian optimisation is the means to find the optimal solution within a very small number of experiments. A Gaussian process is fully defined by a mean function $m(\underline{x})$ and a covariance function $k(\underline{x}, \underline{x}')$. Based on a Gaussian process prior and available data points Gaussian process regression can be performed. Predictions for a process parameter point \underline{x}_* can be made as follows [32]:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_t(\underline{x}_*) &= m(\underline{x}_*) + \underline{k}^T(\underline{x}_*)(\underline{K} + \sigma_N^2 \underline{I})^{-1} (\underline{y}_t - \underline{m}(\underline{x}_{1:t})) \\ \sigma_t^2(\underline{x}_*) &= k(\underline{x}_*, \underline{x}_*) - \underline{k}^T(\underline{x}_*)(\underline{K} + \sigma_N^2 \underline{I})^{-1} \underline{k}(\underline{x}_*) \\ \underline{K} &= \begin{pmatrix} k(\underline{x}_1, \underline{x}_1) & \dots & k(\underline{x}_1, \underline{x}_t) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ k(\underline{x}_t, \underline{x}_1) & \dots & k(\underline{x}_t, \underline{x}_t) \end{pmatrix}\end{aligned}$$

The measurements are assumed to be corrupted by Gaussian noise $N(0, \sigma_N^2)$, which is normally distributed with zero mean and variance σ_N^2 . Here, μ_t is the posterior mean and σ_t^2 denotes the posterior variance. The identity matrix is given by \underline{I} . The mean function vector is defined as $\underline{m}(\underline{x}_{1:t}) = [m(\underline{x}_1) \dots m(\underline{x}_t)]^T$, while the covariance matrix is represented by \underline{K} . The covariance vector is $\underline{k}(\underline{x}_*) = [k(\underline{x}_*, \underline{x}_1) \dots k(\underline{x}_*, \underline{x}_t)]^T$.

The figure below shows the prediction after some measurements (black dots) are available. The prediction uncertainty is reduced to the measurement uncertainty close to the measurements, but further away, it increases. This is intuitive for human operators, but most models do not include uncertainty due to missing data. The prediction from Gaussian process regression can then be used to decide where to sample next. The next sample point should be informative about the optimum. To mathematically find this point, the algorithm needs to balance exploitation and exploration, which is often done by calculating an acquisition function and optimizing it. Details can be found in [37]. Therefore, the next experiment is conducted for parameter points that maximize the acquisition function. After this experiment is completed, the model can be refined, and the next experiments can be determined. This basic approach of Bayesian optimization can be extended to more advanced cases, such as including constraints on the surface roughness of the final part. Constraint Bayesian optimization is demonstrated in [7].

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Figure 6: Functionality of Bayesian optimization. Left: flowchart, right cost function to be optimised over process parameters

Reducing the number of required experiments is of major interest, making it valuable to include prior knowledge, such as known analytical or physics-based models. Bayesian optimization naturally allows for the inclusion of prior knowledge due to its Bayesian formulation.

As an example, a longitudinal turning process was investigated where production costs are to be minimized. The cost function takes into account machine costs and tool exchange costs due to wear. The experiments compare optimization without prior knowledge to models that incorporate prior knowledge. Figure 7 summarizes the different models.

- **Model 1:** The standard model without prior knowledge.
- **Model 2:** Utilizes fixed hyperparameters from previous measurements. This should not be confused with fixed parameters; fixed hyperparameters restrict the function space but do not fix the result to a specific function.
- **Model 3:** Uses the Taylor wear equation for tool wear modelling as prior knowledge.
- **Model 4:** Utilizes data from similar experiments as prior knowledge.

The results of the automatic selection of prior knowledge are shown in Figure 8. The black line represents the standard approach without prior knowledge. All approaches utilizing prior knowledge reduce the number of experiments by at least 40%. This demonstrates the value of combining prior knowledge with measured data to find optimal parameters.

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Figure 7: different variants of Bayesian optimisation [18].

Figure 8: reduction of cost function with the number of experiments for the different model variants [18].

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6. Compensation with AI

The intelligent grinding system shall have an increased autonomy, which means that the monitoring system is not only observing the process but also the health status of the machine and its components and has to adapt the machine to its environment. In precision machining most important is to solve the issue of compensation of the thermal movements of the machine, where a lot of work has been done in the past. It was recognized in [3, 19, 20, 43] that a good alternative to FEM modelling of the machine are self-learning approaches as also the physical equations need for good accuracy a lot of measurements from thermal expansion coefficients to the governing heat transfer coefficients. Figure 9 shows a thermal adaptive learning control (TALC) approach with a simple model based on ARX (autoregressive model with external input) structure. The model is trained as shown in Figure 9 with temperature or power measurements together with dimensional probing between spindle stock and workpiece side. The model calculates individual axis errors and synthesizes from there the displacement at the TCP. The errors of the axes can naturally be directly utilized to compensate the individual axis. In case the probing results deviate too much from those predicted from the model, the model is updated and adapted to the new situation.

Figure 9: TALC approach for the thermal compensation of machine tools based on trained model with ARX structure modified from [2], [43].

The update of the model now shown for a grinding machine in Figure 10 also re-considers the suitability of the temperature sensors in step 1 to 2. The sensor input is normalised and clustered with a support vector machine approach. From each of the clusters only one sensor is selected for the input to the model. The procedure to enhance the compensation strategy is shown in Figure 10c. After some training of the model the machine errors, which can be compensated by the machine axes are suppressed by calculating corrections of the position errors from the compensation model and feeding them to the control. After some time, when deviations between model predictions and the probing results differ too much, the model becomes re-calibrated and at the same time the input selection is repeated.

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Figure 10: Self-learning thermal compensation of a grinding machine, modified from [43]. a.) grinding machine equipped with temperature sensors (red dots), b.) input selection and model update, c.) error compensation after the model calibration phase and model update together with input selection in case the no good (NG) limit is reached.

Figure 11 shows an example of the results of three errors out of 15 identified errors for a long period of time of 1000h with randomly selected motions of the machine, switching on the coolant (blue stripes) and in dry conditions. The dark shaded colors indicate the remaining error after compensation. Figure 12 presents the volumetric error, which is composed from all the individual axes errors and indicates a suppression of thermally induced Root mean square error (RMSE) in the workspace volume by more than 80%. Figure 12 shows that the distribution of errors is shifted in the direction of 0 and especially is narrowed down.

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Figure 11: 3 out of 15 identified axis errors in comparison between the compensated (dark shaded) and uncompensated (light shaded) state. The vertical dotted black lines represent the adaptively triggered state updates, and the horizontal dashed black lines describe the adaptive action control limit (ACL) of the individual thermal errors. The vertical dashed red lines represent an exceedance of the ACLs of all thermal errors. The red areas, which have a width of twelve hours, represent a not to scale interruption between experiments. The light blue areas represent the use of coolant [44].

Figure 12: Top: mean of the uncompensated and compensated volumetric thermal error at the measurement positions of the on-machine measurement for random thermal load cases. The grey area represents the double standard deviation as uncertainty of the volumetric errors. For further explanations, see Figure 11. Bottom: Statistical distribution of the volumetric errors at the measuring positions for different compensation strategies including the 95% quantile represented by the vertical lines and the corresponding reduction [44].

Volumetric RMSE:
 30.7 μm \rightarrow 4.8 μm
 reduction 87%

7. Chatter avoidance

Chatter, regenerative vibrations in cutting with geometrically defined cutting edges is a harsh limit of productivity. It withdraws energy from the continuous rotation into vibration modes until the linearity limit is reached, which often means damage of the work piece, tool or even spindle. Despite heavy research into this topic, only recent solutions based on AI [30], [36], [27] are capable of providing an industrially viable possibility to exploit the conditionally stable regions of cutting parameters as shown in Figure 13. The problem to be overcome is that the peaks of the stability lobe diagram need to be exactly known, because in the direct vicinity damage is threatening. Furthermore, the system is changing all the time, partially on purpose by exchanging tools and tool holders, partly because to unwanted changes due to wear of the tool and the machine. Therefore, physics support of AI to deal with those changes is essential. The algorithm how the dynamic behavior of a system changes in case of addition or removal of system components is known under the name of receptance coupling and roughly shown in Figure 14. Then Figure 15 shows that the subcomponents are individually modelled with NN and the data for training are continuously collected via cutting operations to update the predicted SLD. Also, the tool and tool holder are modelled physically as a composed Timoshenko beam. Training is necessary because the coupling condition between tool and tool holder is difficult to model. The range of unknown parameters is estimated and within their probable range assumed as constant distribution.

Figure 13: physics based and data based approaches to establish stability lobe diagrams and demonstration of the benefits of exploiting the conditionally stable region [30].

Figure 14: Substructuring and receptance coupling as physics based tool for description of changeover of machine tools

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Figure 15: modelling of individual components in the kinematic chain of the MT [30].

Figure 16: Teach-in of the cutting force coefficients during the cutting process [30].

Figure 17 shows the possibilities of federated learning, in which different machines learn the tool inventory together. Due to the use of modular, physical models, the results for the tools and tool holders can be transferred to other machines. Furthermore, the machines can also be exchanged, which is known as fleet or transfer learning, because it is known exactly what influence they exert, and a conversion to the larger or smaller machine type is possible by comparing the transfer function.

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Figure 17: Model based federated learning or fleet learning based on the modular approach [27].

While learning has to deal with randomly distributed training data during an ongoing machining process, targeted learning, e.g. Bayesian learning, can lead to a dramatic reduction in the necessary training data, especially if, as in the case of chatter approaches, the basic behavior of the process is already given. Figure 18 shows an example of this. Here, as stated above, a probability of chattering is derived from a random distribution of the model parameters and coded in the form of gray tones in the stability map. The core of the Bayesian approach is that the training data set is selected using an acquisition function. So where the uncertainty is greatest, the acquisition function coded as a yellow tone is greatest, and that is where the next attempt is requested. Of course, it can be seen that neither an experiment in the safely stable area nor one in the safely unstable area contributes anything to improving knowledge of the stability limit, but rather experiments on the border between stable and unstable are required. After three learning points, the stability map is specified with sufficient precision. The acquisition function was defined independently of the intended cutting parameters. You can also, for example, superimpose a desired speed range on it, so that suggestions for data acquisition come preferably, but not exclusively, from this range. This possibility is offered because even in the area that is not of interest for the execution of the process, very useful information can be drawn for the overall course of the stability limit based on the physical model. The width of the gray veils in the stability maps become narrower with the iterations. They are also often interpreted as the severity of the expected chatter, which may be considered a heuristic but does not stand up to rigorous analysis.

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Figure 18: Bayes learning, selection of training points according to the acquisition function (informativeness function) [27].

The system is based on zero-order stability theory, which, however, excludes its applicability to certain tools such as toothed milling tools and requires an expansion that still needs to be carried out. However, tools that are not covered can be clearly identified and the learning process can then be excluded. Nevertheless, a system is available that can be used on machine tools in everyday machining to avoid chatter.

8. Combat against grinding burn

Grinding burn is the most feared damage happening in grinding. The strong heat generation changes the process signature, especially the microstructure in the subsurface region. Grinding burn happens upon unsuitable selection of process parameters, insufficient cooling and wear of the grinding wheel. While the standard way to deal with grinding burn is to use the Nital-test offline or Barkhausen noise analysis, creating a significant delay between manufacturing and quality check. The situation motivated significant research into the on-machine and in-process detection of grinding burn laid down for instance in [16, 25, 35] largely based on signals from Acoustic Emission (AE) sensors and / or acceleration measurements. The setup of this process monitoring element within the bio-intelligent approach requires a suitable sensoric system together with the data analytics behind. For post processing the data and distilling out some characteristic features and for classification into the different severity classes of grinding burn according to ISO14004 different artificial intelligence tools are used. Figure 19 gives an overview on the sensoric equipment of a circular grinder. Two acoustic emission sensors are placed near the tool and close to the workpiece, having different transfer functions from the source of noise and thus being capable to gain partly complementary elements out of the signals. Furthermore, the current and power over time are detected.

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Figure 19: On machine grinding burn detection, sensoric setup [33].

The justification of the choice of sensors is presented in Table 1 upon different criteria considering also industrialisation.

Table 1: Selection of sensors for process monitoring in grinding [34].

Criterion	AE	Vibration	Current	Power	Forces	Temperature
Suitable for grinding burn detection	●	◐	◑	◑	◑	●
Suitable to estimate abrasive wear	◑	●	◑	●	◑	◐
Suitable for parameter optimization	◑	◐	◐	◑	◑	◐
Costs (sensor & coupler)	◑	●	●	●	◐	○
Mounting and calibration effort	◐	◑	●	●	◐	○
Robustness of the signal	◑	◐	◑	◐	◐	◐

A true sensor fusion approach does not only use the information content of each signal individually, but also merges them with different mathematical operations to finally extract some features, which can indicate the exceptions from normal operation. Features are scalar values characterising the signal itself or its transformation. Transformations applied in literature are according to [34] the Fast-Fourier Transform (FFT), the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), the Wavelet Transform as Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) or Wavelet Package Transform (WPT), the Hilbert Transform in the variants of Hilbert Huang Transform (HHT), Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD), Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD), Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD), MEL Frequency Cepstrum (MFC). The MFC is insofar different from the others and interesting due to its wide application in speech recognition, as it extracts out of the spectrum different frequency ranges by filters and then reconstructs the signal [6], [5], [28]. The next step is the extraction of scalar values, the features from the transformed signals. Again, different possibilities and standards exist, some of which are inspired by surface roughness analysis. In [34] they are described in detail.

The whole pipeline for grinding burn detection running in a job shop for grinding ball screw spindles is shown in Figure 20 starting from the acquisition of original data as time dependent signal values. These are preprocessed by detection of the grinding situation, by picking out a relevant and significant section of the signal, which is then filtered and transformed, such that the features can be computed. The system setup starts with a huge number of different features out of different transforms, which are then reduced by clustering, Support Vector Machine (SVM) univariate filter method (ANOVA) or Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) to in the end 87 most significant features from all 4 sensors.

With the tree based XGBoost or alternatively with deep state space model (DSS) with hyperparameters optimized by Bayesian optimisation, the classification into the grinding burn classes according to ISO 14104

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is realised. With Nital etching the ground specimens are classified experimentally which then is used for reinforcement learning.

Figure 20: On machine grinding burn detection, data processing pipeline and utilisation of classification of grinding burn and intelligent decision making [33].

The training data have been collected with 3 different grinding wheels and 3 different steel materials. The classification into grinding burn according to the predefined threshold was possible with 99% accuracy, while a classification into the 4 ISO 14104-classes was achieved with 98% accuracy. These classification results outperform any other classification so far achieved. It could be proven that omitting the signals of one of the sensors creates a significant loss in classification accuracy, though a reasonable classification result still can be achieved. Furthermore, it was detected that using a grinding wheel unseen by the training still a classification was possible but again with an important loss of classification accuracy.

9. Federated learning for fractal manufacturing

9.1 Connectivity

As illustrated in the visionary Figure 1 all machines, particularly production machines, will in the future leverage the opportunity to learn from other machines. Often, the necessary volume of data for machine learning models is available only when multiple machines are considered in the learning process. Industry adopts two primary strategies: cloud-based solutions operated by machine manufacturers and internal company solutions. The fundamental requirement is always to establish connectivity for the machines within the job shop.

Already in 2016, [12] presented a development pipeline for Industry 4.0, where the initial phase emphasized the unconditional establishment of machine connectivity, transforming them into cyber-physical production systems (CPPS). Data on the status of machines and their components is crucial for establishing predictive maintenance, which remains a primary goal. Because the lifecycle of the product being manufactured intersects with that of the production machine during the processing step digitization and communication between the product as CPS and the production machine as CPPS is especially beneficial. This allows for process adjustments based on the state of the material, and for the collection of both process data and product data on the production machine. This data can then be utilized within the company or via an external cloud-based system.

Real-time data generated by various sensors, CNC, and PLC on the machine are collected by an edge device, as demonstrated in Figure 21. As an example, the SIEMENS Edge Computing Platform for Machine Tools, a commercial solution that facilitates the hosting of applications on a digital platform situated close to the

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shop floor. This proximity enables the enhancement of automation and the deployment of demanding data stream processing and learning algorithms. IIoT platforms, such as these, effectively address a range of industrial operational challenges, including logistics, automation, remote operations, quality control, and maintenance.

Figure 21: Siemens EDGE architectural concept [38]

The exchange of data with different addressees within the company is typically organized in the classical automation pyramid, which provokes heavy data transfer across the hierarchical layers. To address this shortcoming, the RAMI 4.0 reference architecture was established as shown below. The RAMI 4.0 framework allows for the exchange of information without hierarchical constraints. Furthermore, this framework considers the entire lifecycle of production, from development to usage and maintenance. For data exchange to occur in a non-hierarchical manner, it is crucial that each device communicates in the "same language," necessitating standardized data protocols.

Figure 22: RAMI4.0 [29]

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To standardize communication, the UMATI (universal machine tool interface) initiative was launched. The UMATI initiative builds a common semantic framework within the shop floor. UMATI is strongly related to the OPC UA communication protocol, as OPC UA allows for the specification of an information model to structure data. Such information models have been developed by the UMATI initiative, called companion specifications, to standardize data exchange within specific domains. Figure 23 shows the different companion specifications.

At the bottom is the machinery specification, which is suitable for every machine ranging from pumps to machine tools. Then there is a specific companion specification for machine tools. On top of this, we have companion specifications for specific machine tools such as metal forming, laser systems, and additive manufacturing. The machinery and machine specifications were released in 2020, with many specific specifications following in 2023.

RC: Release Candidate

Figure 23: Companion specifications from UMATI for OPC/UA

Although the information models derived from the umati initiative (Companion Specifications) are currently somewhat sparse, they exhibit the highest development speed. Consequently, the following communication model predominantly employs the umati standard (OPC 40501-1 UA for Machine Tools), which defines the following nine different use cases:

1. Machine identification
2. Machine status information
3. Overview of parts in the production order
4. Overview of production order durations
5. Machine condition overview
6. Summary of required operator interventions
7. Overview of error messages and warnings
8. Information for calculating KPIs, including data on media usage and energy consumption
9. Overview of tool data

These use cases can be categorized into three different utilization levels:

A. Machine status: Cases 1, 2, and 3 B. Ongoing production: Cases 3, 4, and 8 C. Maintenance information: Cases 5, 6, 7, and 9.

An additional utilization level for process monitoring (D) is not yet fully developed but is expected to gain importance in the future, currently only partially covered by cases 6 and 8.

Beyond connectivity on the shop floor within a single company, data exchange between different companies is also crucial to leverage the full potential of the data. Figure 24 illustrates the concept of such a platform developed within the EU-MARS project. Manufacturing companies are not only connected internally but also with the platform to exchange data. The platform interacts with customers, allowing them to place orders and receive production status updates. Service providers can also connect to the platform to offer services to manufacturing partners. Moreover, the platform facilitates data exchange with regulators, sharing information such as the CO2 footprint.

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Figure 24: EU-MARS Platform for fractal manufacturing

Another critical aspect of intelligent manufacturing is operational security, which involves protecting the shop floor network from external cyber threats. It is essential to establish a secure infrastructure that safeguards assets while enabling necessary data communication for digitalized machines to function. Architectures are designed to segment different operational levels, as per the RAMI 4.0 layers. Interfaces such as OPC UA, secure MQTT, AMQP, and protected APIs allow digital platforms to securely access data from machines.

9.2 Transfer and Federated Learning

Transfer and federated learning is the solution to provide the necessary amount of data for the vast field of application cases for a fleet of machines.

Transfer learning is defined as a machine learning technique in which a model pre-trained for one task is optimized for a new, related task. With federated learning, models are trained on multiple devices at the same time. This is done decentrally and without any release or exchange of sensitive information. Exchanged between machines or between machines and cloud are only condensed data, for instance model parameters and identifiers of the individual machine.

The problem to be solved is that in machine tools and production machinery really equal machines rarely exist, but they are more or less similar as pointed out in a hierarchy of classes:

- Same machines, same add on equipment, same age
- Same machines same add on equipment, different age
- Same machines, different add on equipment and or different age
- Same series, but different machines, different sizes, different performance data
- Different series, different machines.

If machines are different, local learning on the individual machine typically delivers more suitable models than learning on other machines or model data in the cloud, which is especially true in case

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of machine data like status or compensation model data, while process data might be more easy to directly exchange.

From top to bottom increased computation is necessary to adapt trained models between machines. Even in case of same machines, same equipment and same age differences are encountered. Different approaches are model data transfer n to m meaning from each machine to each other machine which requires n times m translation models or n to 1 , 1 to m , which requires only $n+m$ translation models but with loss of information due to a 2-step approach for each translation. In the cloud only one data driven model, the master model, comprising the information from all machines is generated, an approach, which is shown in Figure 25. The advantage of this solution is that the impact from outside learning models is limited to only one information channel. In case of NN-based models a restricted area for the master model can be set aside a restricted area for the local model can be provided, so that external learning does not damage local learning.

Figure 25: Fleet learning as n to 1 , 1 to m with a master model in the cloud and master machine at the OEM

Other than permanent learning and distribution of data initializing models on new machines is much easier and beneficially for the OEM. Figure 26 shows a procedure for thermal error compensation in this case, drastically reducing the training effort for machine series. Here the most recent master model is used for the initialisation of the AI-model on new machines and from there on all the updates are taking place locally.

Figure 26: Fleet learning of thermal error compensation in machine tools [39].

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A test case for two machine tools learning from each other for thermal compensation with TALC as described in chapter 4 was established as shown in Figure 27. The MTs, named MTV and MTZ, are 5 axis milling machines DMGMori NMV5000 DCG with different equipment, different age and very different environment. MTZ has a C-axis running with 1200 min^{-1} , while the C-axis of MTV was only capable for 120 min^{-1} . MTV is older and placed in a temperature-controlled job shop, while MTZ is exposed to an environment with uncontrolled temperature changes.

Figure 27: Transfer learning configuration for thermal compensation between two 5-axis milling machines MTV and MTZ [40].

This shows that the model learned for MTZ when transferred to the MTV leads to significantly improved behavior and thus significantly shortens the training of the model on the MTV. It can also be seen in Figure 28 that the installation conditions of the MTZ in the non-air-conditioned hall increase the training success and therefore the MTZ as the lead machine has more extensive experience than the MTV.

For continuous gear grinding machines company Reishauer AG developed the system ARGUS [9] as cloud based system for their customers to monitor their machines. This state-of-the-art system for intelligent grinding is composed of edge devices as hardware, software modules to be used by the machine owner and cloud-based apps for the analysis of data, which can be accessed from the Reishauer cloud. The benefit of utilisation of the system is equally shared between machine user and machine manufacturer, which is never achieved with a mere predictive maintenance solution. ARGUS provides the machine user with advice on utilisation of the machine of fast process setup, process monitoring and extraction of quality relevant data, ensuring 100% quality control of each gear. The cloud-based apps facilitate comprehensive analysis and evaluation of all grinding and dressing processes conducted on the machine. These applications, accessible on the cloud, generate a detailed real-time snapshot of all connected grinding machines, inclusive of their full operational history. Cloud-based subscription services like these deliver significant value to end-users, offering affordable, indirect quality control and machine-maintenance support. Simultaneously, such partnership is beneficial for the machine builder as well, providing access to valuable machines' operational data to support the development of next-generation, high-end gear-grinding machines. AI tools trained on the data fed into the cloud enable fleet learning.

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Figure 28: Thermal compensation for four different errors using the phenomenological model on the MTV. Above is the model trained on MTV in use, which still requires a few model adjustments visible as vertical lines within the 72 hours. The transferred trained model from MTZ is used below [40].

10. Conclusion

Artificial intelligence is nowadays due to the availability of powerful computation and research that has taken place on the algorithmic side a really mighty toolbox with an infinite number of tools. Taking advantage of it is mandatory in every application and also in modern manufacturing. The possible applications are by far not fully explored, which is also due to the fact that one of the important challenges is the selection of the most suitable tool. The utilisation of prior knowledge, integration of physical models and equations can be valuable to reduce the greed for data that is the great drawback of all AI and one of the important research topics is to explore how and where physics can help. The Bayesian approach is a possibility to focus the learning to points of interest by that reduce the training expenditure. AI is a real game changer. Being still not comparable to human intelligence, but a mere programmed IT application, it has advantages and disadvantages over human intelligence. The advantage is the fast analysis of large amount of data and missing or artificially installed oblivion. But exactly that demands a redistribution of tasks between humans and machines. “Operator integrated” is therefore a vision of modern manufacturing machines that are capable of taking over tasks that today still are the domain of humans. As all AI requires data, the quality of data plays a major role, and the very beginning of AI projects is the definition of sensory equipment of the machine. To exploit the capability of AI, sensors similar to human sensing like optics and acoustics and the full and tight integration in the data analysis and reasoning of the machine are of interest, driving the field of bio-intelligence in the biological transformation. Application field for application field needs to be examined for possible application and benefit of AI. Especially where physical modelling becomes too complicated, computationally too expensive AI becomes the white knight. Application fields like increase of machining accuracy to combat against thermal errors with permanently adaptive self-learning models is shown, where also the Bayesian approach can be a valuable alternative. The AI solution for detection and prediction of grinding burn demonstrates sensor fusion and a preparation and utilisation channel of process data, which is completely out of the reach of human intelligence. Selection of optimal process parameters shows a very beneficial utilisation of Gaussian processes with Bayesian regression, requiring very limited training cycles. This can also be of interest for the solution of the chatter problem. But here

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massive utilisation of prior physical modelling in combination with AI is the key for being in the meantime capable to offer a viable industrial solution. Transfer of trained models between machines even if they are different to a certain extent is helpful to reduce the major drawback, namely the training effort. Connectivity of machines and the decision which data to process locally and which are transferred to a cloud is the essential pre-requisite. Examples here are thermal compensation of a machine fleet as well as the provision of process parameters via a cloud application from a machine producer. As research proceeds the vision of intelligent, autonomously operating machines via “driver assistants” and partly “driverless applications” will become reality.

References

- [1] Abbasi J, Andersen PØ (2022) Physical activation functions (pafs): An approach for more efficient induction of physics into physics-informed neural networks (pinns). *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2205.14630.
- [2] Blaser P (2020) *Adaptive Learning Control for Thermal Error Compensation*. PhD-thesis No. 26709, ETH Zürich.
- [3] Brecher C, Hirsch P, Weck M (2004) Compensation of Thermo-elastic Machine Tool Deformation Based on Control internal Data. *CIRP Annals*, 53(1): p. 299-304.
- [4] Byrne G, Damm O, Monostori L, Teti R, van Houten F, Wegener K, Wertheim R, Sammler F (2021) Towards high performance living manufacturing systems - A new convergence between biology and engineering. *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, 34: p. 6-21.
- [5] Davis S, Mermelstein P (1980) Comparison of parametric representations for monosyllabic word recognition in continuously spoken sentences. *IEEE Transactions on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, 28(4): p. 357-366.
- [6] Frigieri EP, Campos PHS, Paiva AP, Balestrassi PP, Ferreira JR, Ynoguti CA (2016) A mel-frequency cepstral coefficient-based approach for surface roughness diagnosis in hard turning using acoustic signals and gaussian mixture models. *Applied Acoustics*, 113: p. 230-237.
- [7] Gardner JR, Kusner MJ, Xu ZE, Weinberger KQ, Cunningham JP (2014) Bayesian optimization with inequality constraints. in *31st International Conference on Machine Learning*.p. 937-945.
- [8] Gittler T (2023) *Data acquisition and data analytics or prognostics and health management in machine tools*. PhD-thesis No. 28940, ETH Zürich.
- [9] Graf W (2023) *Reishauer ARGUS Monitoring System*. Available from: https://www.reishauer.com/fileadmin/Dateiliste/Technologie/ARGUS/brochure_argus_en_web.pdf. Accessed 20.6.2023. Reishauer AG: Reishauer, Wallisellen.
- [10] Guo S, Agarwal M, Cooper C, Tian Q, Gao RX, Guo W, Guo YB (2022) Machine learning for metal additive manufacturing: Towards a physics-informed data-driven paradigm. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 62: p. 145-163.
- [11] Gutknecht K, Cloots M, Sommerhuber R, Wegener K (2021) Mutual comparison of acoustic, pyrometric and thermographic laser powder bed fusion monitoring. *Materials & Design*, 210: p. 110036.
- [12] Hunschofsky H, Mauthner G, Magnet C (2016) Hoerbiger 1-1-1 – Turning High-Mix / Low-Volume Manufacturing from a Constraint into a Competitive Advantage. in *WPK 2016, Adaptive and Smart Manufacturing*.p. 139-154.
- [13] Knüttel D, Baraldo S, Valente A, Wegener K, Carpanzano E (2021) Model based learning for efficient modelling of heat transfer dynamics. *Procedia CIRP*, 102: p. 252-257.
- [14] KOCH M, REITERER H, TJOA AM, KOLM P A Manual For Humanized Office Information Systems design. in *4. IFIP TC9 International Conference on Human Choice and Computers, HCC- 4*. Dublin, Ireland: North-Holland, Amsterdam, ISBN 0-444-88759-8.p. 327-336.

Appendix 5

- [15] Kolb AY, Kolb DA (2008) The Learning Way: Meta-cognitive Aspects of Experiential Learning. *Simulation & Gaming*, 40(3): p. 297-327.
- [16] Kwak J-S, Ha M-K (2004) Detection of dressing time using the grinding force signal based on the discrete wavelet decomposition. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 23(1): p. 87-92.
- [17] Li T, Zhao Z, Sun C, Cheng L, Chen X, Yan R, Gao RX (2021) WaveletKernelNet: An interpretable deep neural network for industrial intelligent diagnosis. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems.*, 52(4): p. 2302–2312.
- [18] Maier M (2022) *Autonomous Parameter Selection of Manufacturing Processes with Applications in Grinding and Turning*. PhD-thesis No. 28002, ETH Zurich.
- [19] Mareš M, Horejš O, Havlík L (2020) Thermal error compensation of a 5-axis machine tool using indigenous temperature sensors and CNC integrated Python code validated with a machined test piece. *Precision Engineering*, 66: p. 21-30.
- [20] Mayr J, Blaser P, Ryser A, Hernandez-Becerro P (2018) An adaptive self-learning compensation approach for thermal errors on 5-axis machine tools handling an arbitrary set of sample rates. *CIRP Annals*, 67(1): p. 551-554.
- [21] McCann R, Obeidi MA, Hughes C, McCarthy É, Egan DS, Vijayaraghavan RK, Joshi AM, Acinas Garzon V, Dowling DP, McNally PJ, Brabazon D (2021) In-situ sensing, process monitoring and machine control in Laser Powder Bed Fusion: A review. *Additive Manufacturing*, 45: p. 102058.
- [22] Meng C, Seo S, Cao D, Griesemer S, Liu Y (2022) When physics meets machine learning: A survey of physics-informed machine learning. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2203.16797.
- [23] Minh D, Wang HX, Li YF, Nguyen TN (2022) Explainable artificial intelligence: a comprehensive review. *Artificial Intelligence Review*, 55(5): p. 3503-3568.
- [24] Möhring HC, Wiederkehr P, Erkorkmaz K, Kakinuma Y (2020) Self-optimizing machining systems. *CIRP Annals*, 69(2): p. 740-763.
- [25] Neto R *Monitoring of grinding burn by AE and vibration signals*, in ICAART, Martins Chr Marchi M, De Aguiar Pr, Bianchi Ec, Editor. p. 272–279.
- [26] Ng WX, Chan HK, Teo WK, Chen IM (2017) Capturing the tacit knowledge of the skilled operator to program tool paths and tool orientations for robot belt grinding. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 91(5): p. 1599-1618.
- [27] Ostad Ali Akbari V (2024) *Physics-informed Probabilistic Artificial Intelligence for Enhanced Stability Predictions in Milling*. PhD-thesis, ETH Zürich.
- [28] Picone JW (1993) Signal modeling techniques in speech recognition. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 81(9): p. 1215-1247.
- [29] *Plattform Industrie 4.0: RAMI4.0 – a reference framework for digitalisation*: https://www.plattform-i40.de/IP/Redaktion/EN/Downloads/Publikation/rami40-an-introduction.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=7. Accessed 31.7.2024.
- [30] Postel M (2020) *Model-supported Improvement of Stability Limit Predictions in Milling Through Artificial Neural Networks*. PhD-thesis No. 26709, ETH Zürich.
- [31] Raissi M, Perdikaris P, Karniadakis GE (2019) Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 378: p. 686-707.
- [32] Rasmussen CE, Williams CKI (2006) *Gaussian processes for machine learning*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press.
- [33] Sauter E, Sarikaya E, Winter M, Wegener K (2021) In-process detection of grinding burn using machine learning. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 115(7): p. 2281-2297.
- [34] Sauter E (2023) *Detection and avoidance of thermal damage for high-performance metal grinding processes using hybrid machine learning models*. PhD-thesis No. 29055, ETH Zürich.
- [35] Saxler W (1997) *Erkennung von Schleifbrand durch Schallemissionsanalyse*. VDI-Verlag.

Appendix 5

- [36] Schmitz T, Cornelius A, Karandikar J, Tyler C, Smith S (2022) Receptance coupling substructure analysis and chatter frequency-informed machine learning for milling stability. *CIRP Annals*, 71(1): p. 321-324.
- [37] Shahriari B, Swersky K, Wang Z, Adams RP, Freitas Nd (2016) Taking the Human Out of the Loop: A Review of Bayesian Optimization. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 104(1): p. 148-175.
- [38] Siemens AG (2024) *Industrial Edge for Machine Tools, a Siemens Edge Computing Platform for the Machine Tool Domain*: Available from: <https://documentation.mindsphere.io/resources/html/manage-my-sinumerik-edge-app-management/en-US/user-docu/industrialedge.html#architectural-concept-overview>. Accessed: 31.7.2024.
- [39] Stoop F, Mayr J, Sulz C, Bleicher F, Wegener K (2021) Fleet learning of thermal error compensation in machine tools. in *2021 26th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)* .p. 1-4.
- [40] Stoop F, Mayr J, Sulz C, Kaftan P, Bleicher F, Yamazaki K, Wegener K (2023) Cloud-based thermal error compensation with a federated learning approach. *Precision Engineering*, 79: p. 135-145.
- [41] Wegener K, Spierings AB, Teti R, Caggiano A, Knüttel D, Staub A (2021) A conceptual vision for a bio-intelligent manufacturing cell for Selective Laser Melting. *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, 34: p. 61-83.
- [42] Yang L, Zhang D, Karniadakis GE (2020) Physics-informed generative adversarial networks for stochastic differential equations. . *SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing*, 42(1): p. A292-A317.
- [43] Zimmermann N, Büchi T, Mayr J, Wegener K (2022) Self-optimizing thermal error compensation models with adaptive inputs using Group-LASSO for ARX-models. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 64: p. 615-625.
- [44] Zimmermann N, Müller E, Lang S, Mayr J, Wegener K (2023) Thermally compensated 5-axis machine tools evaluated with impeller machining tests. *CIRP Journal of Manufacturing Science and Technology*, 46: p. 19-35.